

Ecotoxicological Monitoring Protocol for Lagoon Ecosystems

Guidelines and protocol for integrated monitoring in lagoon environments to assess ecotoxicological and climate change impacts

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Date of release: 29/03/2026

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.19315529

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Introduction

This document has been developed with the aim of providing an operational tool for the monitoring of lagoon ecosystems in the framework of the E-TRACE “E-TRACE Ecotoxicological Monitoring Protocols for Lagoon Ecosystems” Project. Lagoons are transitional environments of high ecological relevance, characterized by complex interactions between marine and terrestrial processes. These systems are highly sensitive to the effects of climate change, eutrophication, and pollution arising from multiple anthropogenic pressures, which can significantly alter their ecological balance and impair essential ecosystem functions.

To contribute to the protection and sustainable management of these environments, the E-TRACE project was developed. The E-TRACE project aims to develop a novel methodology for assessing environmental risks associated with anthropogenic activities and their synergistic interactions with climate change impacts on biodiversity and ecologically valuable ecosystems. The project was designed to address the need for mitigation and adaptation strategies based on the assessment of contamination levels in critical habitats, such as lagoon ecosystems, and on the evaluation of potential ecotoxicological impacts. Its ultimate goal is to optimize and implement multi-layered risk assessment approaches to support a comprehensive evaluation of ecosystem integrity and potential implications for human health. Within the framework of E-TRACE, the Orbetello Lagoon was selected as a pilot area. This lagoon represents an ecosystem of outstanding ecological importance but is subjected, at various sites, to significant anthropogenic pressures, including wastewater discharges with different treatment levels, effluents from aquaculture facilities, and multiple contamination sources such as a decommissioned industrial plant formerly dedicated to fertilizer production.

The overarching objective of the project is to test and validate a multidisciplinary investigation methodology that can subsequently be transferred and applied to other Mediterranean areas of high ecological value.

These monitoring protocols provide essential guidelines for implementing an integrated and multidisciplinary strategy aimed at assessing both ecotoxicological impacts and the effects of climate change on lagoon ecosystems. Specifically, the document outlines methodologies for sampling abiotic (water and sediment) and biotic (target bioindicator species) matrices, offering detailed operational guidance to ensure accurate sample collection, handling, and preservation. Furthermore, it describes analytical procedures for the detection of legacy contaminants (e.g., heavy metals, organochlorine compounds) and emerging contaminants (e.g., flame retardants, plasticizers, microlitter) in different environmental matrices, as well as the application of various biomarkers in vertebrate and invertebrate bioindicator species.

Finally, the guideline includes a methodological framework for assessing biodiversity through environmental DNA (eDNA) analysis and for evaluating the synergistic effects of multiple stressors by means of classical toxicity assays.

1. Selection of Sampling Sites

The selection of the sampling sites within the target study area several criteria should be considered in order to apply a robust and representative sampling plan with the aim of applying a multidisciplinary approach and obtaining a comprehensive understanding of the ecotoxicological status and the impacts of climate change in a lagoon ecosystem.

It is, thus, essential to consider:

- Morphological and structural features of the area (such as channels and basins, protected or ecologically important areas, river or canal mouths, and lagoon depth and extension).
- Anthropogenic pressures on the area (including urban discharges, wastewater inputs, industrial activities, agricultural practices, and other human-related activities such as aquaculture facilities).

The selection criteria for sampling site should be:

- Ensure maximum heterogeneity
- Include areas with different current influences
- Select sites near anthropogenic zones
- Cover less impacted or remote areas

This approach makes it possible to account for a wider range of conditions and to gain a more comprehensive understanding of how, and to what extent, the various impacts and factors considered affect the ecotoxicological status of the lagoon. An example of the distribution of sampling sites within the E-TRACE project in the Orbetello Lagoon is reported in Figure 1

Figure 1. Sampling sites in the Orbetello Lagoon within the E-TRACE project. Potential sources of contamination (in red) and the WWF oasis (in green) are highlighted. The lagoon's connections to the open sea are also shown. Sampling sites selected for the study are indicated.

2. Survey Frequency and Environmental Matrices

Sampling should be conducted in at least two distinct seasons to assess the ecotoxicological status of the lagoon under varying environmental conditions. Seasonal variations in parameters such as temperature, pH, salinity, and oxygenation should be considered to select representative periods while avoiding episodes of extreme environmental stress (e.g. heatwaves) that could produce atypical analytical responses. This approach will allow for the assessment of the potential influence of seasonality on the health status of the lagoon, as well as the evaluation of the possible impacts of climate change on the lagoon ecosystem over time.

For example, excessively high temperatures can affect the oxygen concentration in the water, potentially causing mass mortality of organisms and leading to ecological imbalance.

In order to assess the ecotoxicological and climate change impacts in lagoon environments, it is essential to adopt a multidisciplinary approach and to analyse a comprehensive set of environmental matrices.

These should include abiotic and biotic matrices:

- water (both surface and water column)
- sediments
- bioindicators organisms (both vertebrate and invertebrate species, if possible)

3. Physicochemical parameters

3.1 Acquisition methods

Monitoring the physicochemical parameters of lagoon waters allows for the assessment of the lagoon's environmental quality during the sampling period. The determination of these parameters can be carried out either through the use of multiparameter probes (in which case measurements should be taken at regular intervals throughout the monitoring period) or by using data collected from fixed monitoring stations or data loggers installed in the lagoon for the duration of the monitoring activities. The main physicochemical parameters to be assessed may include:

- Temperature (T)
- pH
- Redox potential (Eh)
- Dissolved oxygen (DO)
- Electrical conductivity

All sampling information should be recorded on the Sampling Data Sheet (see Annex, Table A1). The integration of physicochemical data with other datasets obtained during the monitoring activities provides additional data to be integrated with other parameters for a comprehensive understanding of the ecotoxicological status of the lagoon and supports the evaluation of its responses to climate changes.

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4. Water Samples for Microlitter and Environmental DNA Analysis

The sampling design adopted in the E-TRACE project for the Orbetello Lagoon to collect water samples for microlitter and environmental DNA (eDNA) analyses is illustrated in Figure 4.

4.1 Water Samples for Microlitter Analysis

4.1.1 Sampling methods (surface and water column)

In order to assess the microlitter occurrence and distribution within a lagoon, it is crucial to account for both floating particles on the water surface and those potentially dispersed throughout the water column as a consequence of their shape and distinct polymeric properties.

Surface Water Sampling

For surface water sampling in lagoons, net-based methods such as the manta trawl and the WP2 plankton net are recommended. The net should be as compact and manageable as possible, and proportional to the size of the available boat, to facilitate efficient sampling operations in the lagoon environment. To collect a broader range of microlitter and avoid underestimating the presence of smaller particles, it is recommended to use a net with a reduced mesh size (smaller than the commonly

used 300 μm). In case of eutrophic environments, instead, it is preferable to use a larger mesh size of the net (e.g., 330 μm).

General guidelines for surface microlitter sampling in a lagoon environment with a small boat:

- Use a **WP2 plankton net** (Figure 2) with a diameter of 40 cm, a net length of 1 m, and a mesh size of 100 μm
- Tow the WP2 net for a minimum of 10-15 minutes at a vessel speed of less than 3 knots
- Perform sampling under low wind conditions (0–2 on the Beaufort scale)
- Equip the WP2 net with a flow meter to determine the volume of water filtered (m^3)
- Record the start and end positions with GPS, as well as the track, to calculate the surface area sampled (m^2)
- All sampling information should be recorded on the Sampling Data Sheet (see Annex, Table A2).

Figure 2. WP2 plankton net, recommended for microlitter sampling with small boats.

After completion of each tow, thoroughly rinse the WP2 net with pre-filtered water from the outside to the inside to ensure that all particles are directed toward the end of the net and to minimize the risk of contamination. The material retained in the cod-end should then be transferred into glass jars containing 70% ethanol and stored at 4 °C until laboratory analysis. If a large volume of water is required to collect all microlitter particles retained by the net, the sample can be filtered a second time using a sieve with the same mesh size as the net and then transferred into glass jars. The glass jars should be labelled with the sample ID, date, sampling site, and type of analysis.

Water Column Sampling

For **water column** sampling in a lagoon, it is recommended to use the **WP2 plankton net** to perform vertical hauls from the bottom to the surface; this allows for the assessment of microlitter throughout the entire water column. In this case, several guidelines for microlitter sampling throughout the water column are the same as for surface sampling, including net characteristics, flow meter use, and low wind conditions. Additionally, general guidelines for microlitter sampling throughout the entire water column in a lagoon environment are as follows:

- The haul should be conducted at a controlled, steady ascent rate to ensure representative sampling throughout the water column.
- The sampling point should be recorded with GPS.
- The depth at the sampling point should be measured to calculate the volume and surface area sampled (m^2).
- All sampling information should be recorded on the Sampling Data Sheet (see Annex, Table A2).

After each vertical haul, the WP2 net should be thoroughly rinsed with pre-filtered water, following the same procedure described for surface water sampling, including sample collection and storage.

Water Column Sampling at a Specific Depth

For the isolation of microlitter in the water column, including particles smaller than $100\ \mu m$, the use of a new methodology, the ***in-situ pump technique***, is recommended. This method involves *in-situ* filtration of water pumped from a specific depth using a peristaltic pump through a filtration apparatus composed of stainless-steel filters with variable mesh sizes, from $100\ \mu m$ down to $20\ \mu m$.

General guidelines for water column microlitter sampling from specific depths in a lagoon environment:

- The sampling point should be at least 1.5 m below the water surface, or at mid-depth of the water column.
- The filtration apparatus should consist of at least two filters in series: one with a $100\ \mu m$ mesh and one with a $20\ \mu m$ mesh (Figure 3).
- The filtration apparatus should be equipped with a flow meter to determine the volume of water filtered (m^3).
- The sampling should include a minimum of 100 L of water, ideally filtering the equivalent of $1\ m^2$ of water.
- All sampling information should be recorded on the Sampling Data Sheet (see Annex, Table A2).
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Figure 3. Filtration apparatus used for sampling microlitter from the water column, and an example of the filter after use.

At the end of sampling, the filtration apparatus is opened, and the filters carefully rinsed with pre-filtered water into glass jars that had been previously cleaned with the same water. Labels on containers shall include sample ID, date, site, and type of analysis. The jars should be then hermetically sealed and stored at 4 °C in 70% ethanol until laboratory analysis.

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4.1.2 Contamination control

To minimize airborne contamination during both surface and water column sampling, all materials, including the WP2 net, filters, and other instruments used for the *in-situ* pump survey, should be thoroughly rinsed with 0.22 µm filtered water. In addition, several procedural blanks should be performed by rinsing pre-cleaned filters and the WP2 net, with the resulting wash water collected in glass jars for subsequent laboratory analysis as part of QA/QC contamination control.

4.1.3 List of Materials and Equipment

The following material and equipment are necessary to carry out water sampling (surface the water column).

Materials and equipment	Details	Purpose
WP2 plankton net	Equipped with a flow meter, 100 µm mesh size	Surface and water column microlitter sampling
In-situ pump	Equipped with a flow meter, a filtration apparatus with at least two stainless-steel filters of different mesh sizes	Water column microlitter sampling, particles <100 µm
Glass jars with caps	Previously rinsed with pre-filtered water	Sample collection and storage

GPS	Standard GPS device	Recording sampling locations
Pre-filtered water	0.22 µm filtered water	Rinsing equipment and minimizing contamination
Cool box	Insulated storage	Maintaining sample temperature (4 °C)
Funnel (Ø 20 cm)	Standard laboratory funnel	Transferring samples into jars
Latex gloves, powder-free	Standard disposable laboratory gloves	Contamination prevention during sampling
Sieve	With the same mesh size as the net	Reducing the water volume of the samples
Tweezers, spoon	Stainless steel	Transferring particles into jars
Large bowl or washbasin	Stainless steel, ≥5 L	Preventing spillage of samples when emptying cod-end or sieves
Ethanol	Preservation solution (70%)	Preserving samples for storage and transport
Sampling data sheet	Standardized form	Recording sampling metadata and field observations

4.1.4 Sample Preparation and Analytical Parameters for Microlitter Assessment

For the analysis of microlitter in collected water samples, the key parameters to be considered are the number of particles present and their physio-chemical characteristics, such as size, morphology, colour, and polymer type.

This approach ensures that the results are comparable across different studies and sampling campaigns, allowing harmonized interpretation. To isolate microlitter from the collected samples, the samples shall be filtered through a nylon mesh with the same mesh size as that used during sampling. The samples shall then be examined under a stereomicroscope, and all particles considered potentially anthropogenic shall be isolated and classified according to their size, morphology, colour. Subsequently, at least 10% of the isolated particles shall be analysed for polymer composition using spectroscopic techniques such as FTIR, µFTIR, Raman, or µRaman spectroscopy. To obtain harmonized and comparable data with those reported in the literature, it is recommended to classify the particles according to standardized guidelines; for example, by referring to the Recommended Monitoring Methodologies for Microlitter described in the “Guidance on the Monitoring of Marine Litter in European Seas” developed by the European Commission, Joint Research Centre, and the MSFD Technical Group on Marine Litter (2023).

The following parameters/data should be recorded during the analysis in order to obtain data comparable with other studies:

- The volume of water filtered
- The depth at which the sample was collected
- The number of isolated anthropogenic particles
- Whether naturally derived anthropogenic particles (such as cotton, rayon, or wool fibres) were considered

- The different types of particles (shape, colour, size, and polymer type) classified according to standardized methodologies
- The analytical limitations (e.g., the smallest particle isolated, the mesh size used during sample filtration, and the detection limits of the instrument employed for polymer identification)
- The percentage of the sample analysed
- The percentage of particles for which polymer identification was performed
- The use of procedural blanks

4.1.5 Expression of the results

The number of microlitter particles isolated from the water samples shall be normalized to the volume of water filtered. Depending on the monitoring objectives, the final data shall be expressed as items/m³, items/m², or items/km². Furthermore, microlitter is generally characterized by the relative proportions (%) of each category, including shape, colour, size, and polymer type.

4.2. Water Samples for Environmental DNA Analysis

4.2.1 Sampling methods

To assess the metazoan biodiversity of the Lagoon, several methods could be used. Among these, water samples can be collected and subjected to environmental DNA (eDNA) analysis. Sampling sites should be selected in relation to those used for analysing other parameters (e.g., microplastic and contaminant levels), to relate biodiversity data to the other measured parameters.

Below are reported some operational suggestions for sample collection:

- Collect at least 1 L of water per sampling site, or 1 L obtained from three nearby points around the sampling site, to increase data reliability.
- Collect water just below the surface using sterile bottles.
- Use only sterile materials during sampling to minimize contamination.
- All sampling information should be recorded on the Sampling Data Sheet (see Annex, Table A2).

Collected samples should be filtered as soon as possible. If water samples are processed on-site, the filters should be immediately stored at -20 °C or -80 °C until DNA extraction. If on-site filtration is impossible, samples should be transported to the lab, maintaining under dark and at 4 °C. If longer storage is required, samples should be kept at -20 °C until laboratory analysis. Labels on containers shall include sample ID, date, site, and type of analysis.

4.2.2 List of Materials and Equipment

The following material and equipment are necessary to carry out water sampling target to eDNA analysis.

Materials and Equipment	Details	Purpose
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Glass or plastic sterile sampling bottles	Minimum 1 L, sterile	Collection of water samples for eDNA analysis
Vacuum pump apparatus	Sterile apparatus	Water samples filtration on-site
Sterile sampling materials	Gloves, parafilm, sterile handling tools	Preventing contamination during sampling and seal sampling bottles
Cool box	Insulated box with ice packs	Maintaining sample cooled and shielded from light during transport
GPS device	Standard GPS device	Recording sampling locations
Sampling data sheet	Standardized form	Recording sampling metadata and field observations

4.2.3 Sample Preparation and Analytical Parameters

Once in the laboratory, for the analysis of eDNA from lagoon water, samples shall be filtered using a vacuum pump under sterile conditions and using filter membranes capable of retaining DNA fragments. It is therefore essential to consider the average size of the DNA fragments targeted for isolation; for instance, vertebrate DNA fragments are generally smaller than 10 μm (Shu et al., 2020). The filters commonly employed for this purpose are made of nitrocellulose, a material with high affinity for DNA compared to other commonly employed filtration materials (Djurhuus et al., 2017; Sanches and Schreier, 2020), and typically have a pore size ranging between 0.2 and 1.2 μm (Eichmiller et al., 2016). Following filtration, total eDNA shall be extracted using commercial extraction kits such as DNeasy PowerWater (Qiagen), in accordance with the manufacturer’s protocol. The extracted DNA shall be quantified using fluorimetric methods, such as Qubit 4 (Invitrogen), which are specific for dsDNA and are less affected by contamination (proteins, phenol, ethanol, etc.) than absorbance-based methods. The DNA integrity shall also be evaluated using automated electrophoresis (Agilent 2100 Bioanalyser or equivalent). Samples having insufficient DNA integrity (e.g., DNA integrity number below 4) should be discarded from the analysis.

To maximise the detection probability of macroinvertebrates and vertebrates species, it is suggested performing metabarcoding analysis, using previously tested and published primers pairs (Table 1). It is advisable to employ more than one barcode target region to increase the capability of biodiversity detection or otherwise perform a small-scale pilot study to select the most efficient primer pair to be used.

The sequencing libraries are prepared amplifying the target regions by PCR. The final libraries are normalized, pooled, and quantified using KAPA Library Quantification kits for Illumina Sequencing platforms (Kapa Biosystems) or other equivalent methods. Libraries quality shall also be checked though automated electrophoresis systems. Amplicon sequencing is finally performed in 300 bp paired-end format (or appropriate size according to the selected amplicon), using high-throughput sequencing platforms (e.g. Illumina MiSeq™).

Table 1. Primers frequently used successfully in published scientific studies for biodiversity assessment through eDNA metabarcoding analysis in lagoon and marine environments.

Gene target	Primer name	Sequence (5'->3')	Length (bp)	Reference
MT-12S	Tele02	Fw: AAACTCGTGCCAGCCACC	167	(Cananzi et al., 2022; Maiello et al., 2024)
		Rv: GGGTATCTAATCCCAGTTTG		
COI	mICOLintF	Fw: GGWACWGGWTGAACWGTWTAYCCYCC	313	(Leray et al., 2013; Suarez-Menendez et al., 2020)
	jpgHCO2198	Rv: TAIACYTCIGGRTGICRAARAAYCA		
MT-16S	MarVer3F	Fw: AGACGAGAAGACCCTRTG	245	(Valsecchi et al., 2021, 2020)
	MarVer3R	Rv: GGATTGCGCTGTTATCCC		
MT-18S	TAReuk454FWD1	Fw: CCAGCASCYCGGGTAATTCC	400	(Di Capua et al., 2021; Lavrador et al., 2024)
	TAReukREV3	Rv: ACTTTCGTTCTTGATYRATGA		

The following parameters should be recorded during the analytical procedures before sequencing:

- Volume of water filtered
- Concentration and integrity of extracted DNA
- Concentration and integrity of DNA libraries

4.2.4 Expression of the results

The biodiversity results shall include the number of species and taxa detected at each taxonomy level available. The results can also be elaborated through the calculation of commonly employed biodiversity indexes, both describing alpha diversity (e.g., Shannon's diversity index, Gini-Simpson diversity index), and beta diversity (e.g., Bray-Curtis distance).

Figure 4. An example of the sampling design used in the Orbetello Lagoon within the E-TRACE project for water sample collection. This design was applied at each sampling site shown in Figure 1.

5. Sediment Samples for Microlitter, Contaminant, Ecotoxicological bioassay and Environmental DNA Analysis

5.1 Sampling methods

For sediment sampling in a lagoon, samples shall be collected from multiple sites around a single sampling point to ensure a representative and homogeneous sample. The sampling design adopted in the E-TRACE project for the Orbetello Lagoon to collect sediment samples for microlitter, contaminant, ecotoxicological bioassay, and eDNA analysis is illustrated in Figure 5.

Samples may be pooled or analysed individually. The following requirements apply to sediment sample collection:

- The upper 5 cm of sediment shall be collected, for example, using a grab sampler (such as a Van Veen or Box corer).

- A minimum of 1.5 kg shall be collected per site, including at least 3 points per sampling site (total ~4.5 kg per sampling site).
- For microplastic analyses, ~1.5 kg of subsample shall be collected.
- For contaminant analyses, at least 150 g of subsample shall be collected per contaminant class to be analysed.
- For toxicity bioassays, at least two replicates of 750 g each shall be collected, and the sediment should be covered by at least two layers of overlying water to obtain elutriates.
- For eDNA analysis, approximately 40 g of sample shall be collected from multiple sites around a single sampling point and preserved in a sterile container such as a 50 ml Falcon tube or sterile bags.
- All sampling information should be recorded on the Sampling Data Sheet (see Annex, Table A3).

Collected samples shall be stored in clean glass jars, bags, or sterile containers. Labels on containers shall include sample ID, date, site, and type of analysis. Samples for microplastics and toxicity bioassay analyses shall be kept at +4 °C, whereas samples for eDNA and contaminant analyses shall be stored at -20 °C.

5.2 List of materials and equipment

The materials and equipment listed below are required to carry out sediment sampling for microlitter, contaminant, and eDNA analysis.

Materials and Equipment	Details	Purpose
Grab sampler	Suitable for collecting the top 5 cm of sediment	Sediment collection at each sampling site
Balance (scale)	Precision ±1 g	Weighing sediment samples
Glass jars with caps	Pre-cleaned and rinsed with pre-filtered water	Sample collection and storage
Bags	Contaminant-free	Temporary storage or transport of subsamples
Falcon tubes or sterile bags	Sterile containers capable of holding ~40 g of sample	Preservation and storage of eDNA subsamples
GPS device	Standard GPS device	Recording sampling locations
Spatulas or spoons	Stainless steel or inert material	Handling, mixing, and homogenizing sediment samples
Cooler box	Insulated box with ice packs	+4 °C for microplastics/toxicity; -20 °C for contaminants and eDNA
Powder-free latex gloves	Standard disposable laboratory gloves	Contamination prevention during sampling

Sampling data sheet	Standardized form	Recording sample metadata and field observations
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5.3 Sample Preparation and Analytical Parameters

5.3.1 Microlitter Assessment

For the analysis of microlitter in sediment samples, the analytical parameters to be considered are the same as those for water samples, including size, morphology, colour, and polymer type.

For the isolation of microlitter from sediment samples, it is recommended to use density separation solutions that allow the separation of microlitter particles from the sediment. Suitable solutions include zinc chloride ($ZnCl_2$), sodium iodide (NaI), sodium polytungstate ($NaWO_4$), potassium carbonate (K_2CO_3), sodium bromide (NaBr), and potassium formate (HCO_2K), with a minimum density of 1.5 g/cm^3 and preferably greater than 1.7 g/cm^3 , as also recommended in the guidelines developed by the European Commission, Joint Research Centre, and the MSFD Technical Group on Marine Litter (2023).

The samples shall then be examined under a stereomicroscope, and all particles considered potentially anthropogenic shall be isolated and classified according to their size, morphology, and colour. Subsequently, the isolated particles shall be analysed for polymer composition using spectroscopic techniques such as FTIR, μ FTIR, Raman, or μ Raman spectroscopy. It is recommended to classify microlitter according to standardized guidelines; for example, by referring to the Recommended Monitoring Methodologies for Microlitter described in the “Guidance on the Monitoring of Marine Litter in European Seas” developed by the European Commission, Joint Research Centre, and the MSFD Technical Group on Marine Litter (2023).

To normalize the number of isolated particles of microlitter by the amount of sample analysed, it is recommended to record the quantity of sediment analysed as dry weight (grams of the sample weighed after drying at $105 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, according to ISO 11465:1993 (2020)).

The following parameters should be documented during the analysis to ensure comparability with data from other studies:

- The volume of sediment samples analysed
- The dry weight of sediment samples
- The depth at which the sample was collected
- The number of isolated anthropogenic particles
- Whether naturally derived anthropogenic particles (such as cotton, rayon, or wool fibres) were considered
- The different types of particles (shape, colour, size, and polymer type) classified according to standardized methodologies
- The analytical limitations (e.g., the smallest particle isolated, the mesh size used during sample filtration, and the detection limits of the instrument employed for polymer identification)
- The percentage of the sample analysed
- The percentage of particles for which polymer identification was performed

Expression of the results

The number of microlitter particles isolated from sediment samples should be normalized to the amount of sediment analysed. Typically, the final results are expressed as items per kilogram of sediment on a dry weight basis (items/kg dw). Additionally, the relative proportions (%) of microlitter by category, such as shape, colour, size, and polymer type, are typically reported.

5.3.2 Contaminant Analysis

In order to achieve a comprehensive evaluation of contaminants potentially accumulating in the sediments of the investigated area, it is essential to analyse a broad range of pollutant classes associated with anthropogenic pressures. These comprise traditional contaminants, such as pesticides, organochlorine compounds (e.g., PCBs, HCB, and DDT), and heavy metals (Hg, Pb, Cd), as well as emerging pollutants, including perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and plastic-related compounds such as phthalates (PAEs) and brominated flame retardants (PBDE).

For the analysis of these contaminants in sediments, a portion of each sample should be freeze-dried and subsequently processed following the most appropriate methodology according to the contaminant class. For organochlorine compounds (OCs), the analytical procedure EPA 8081/8082, with modifications as described by Capanni et al. (2024), can be applied using capillary gas chromatography.

Phthalates can be extracted following the method proposed by Santini et al. (2024), slightly modified for sediment matrices. The procedure involves extraction and purification steps using QuEChERS, followed by analysis through gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC–MS).

Perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) can be analysed according to established sediment methodologies, such as EPA 8327. The analytical workflow includes extraction and purification using solid-phase extraction (SPE) cartridges, with final determination performed by liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (LC–MS/MS) (Rehman et al., 2023).

The determination of heavy metals, such as mercury, can be carried out by atomic absorption spectrometry using the cold vapor technique (CVAAS) on the <math><63 \mu\text{m}</math> dry sediment fraction, following acid digestion in aqua regia using a microwave digestion system. Other trace metals can be quantified by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP–MS). The analysis of procedural blanks and the use of certified standard reference materials (SRMs) ensure data quality and analytical accuracy.

During the analytical procedures, the following parameters should be recorded:

- The number of samples analysed
- The water content of the sample
- The granulometric composition of the sediment

Expression of the results

The amount of contaminants measured in sediment can be expressed in different ways, depending on their abundance and on how they are commonly reported in the literature (e.g., ng/g, mg/kg). Values are generally reported on a dry weight basis.

5.3.3 Ecotoxicological bioassays

To assess the synergistic effects of multiple stressors, classical toxicity assays shall be conducted on selected model species (e.g., *Daphnia magna* and echinoderm larvae) exposed to elutriates prepared from sediment samples. The testing plan shall include species representing different trophic levels. During toxicity testing, combined stress conditions, such as the presence of conventional and emerging contaminants, microlitter, and variations in temperature and pH (as proxies for climate change), may be simulated under both acute and chronic exposure scenarios. Measured endpoints (e.g., mortality, LC₅₀, LD₅₀, etc.) shall be compared with contaminant concentrations measured in the environment (Campani et al., 2020). The preparation of elutriates can be performed according to ICRAM (2021), which specifies that elutriates should be prepared within 10 days of sediment sampling. For elutriate preparation, natural seawater with a salinity of approximately 30‰, or the culture medium corresponding to the toxicity assays, may be used, maintaining a dilution ratio of 1:4 (sediment dry weight to water volume). The elutriate is obtained by vigorous mechanical agitation of the sediment-water mixture, followed by centrifugation; the supernatant (i.e., the elutriate) is then collected and used for the assays.

The following parameters should be recorded during the analytical procedures:

- Initial amount of sediment sample used for elutriate preparation
- Grain size distribution of the sediment
- pH, salinity, and temperature of each elutriate prior to each assay
- Test species used in the toxicity assays
- Test endpoint (e.g., growth, reproduction, bioluminescence, development)
- Exposure type (acute/chronic)

Expression of the results

Depending on the endpoint (e.g., growth, reproduction, bioluminescence, development), test results are generally expressed as the percentage of organisms in which the endpoint was observed relative to the total number of individuals analysed. The temperature at which the test was conducted, whether the exposure was acute or chronic, and the concentration of the tested elutriate are also typically reported.

5.3.4 Environmental DNA Analysis

Assessing sediment biodiversity using a metagenome approach allows the characterization of the abundant microbial communities of the lagoon environments. Therefore, environmental and microbial DNA shall be extracted and analysed following standardized procedures. To preserve the microbiome composition, it is advisable to store samples at -20 °C or -80 °C upon collection, to avoid microbial proliferation. Before proceeding to the DNA extraction, residual water should be removed from the sediment by centrifugation (e.g., 1000g for 2 min). Once the aqueous fraction has been removed, total DNA can be extracted from 200 – 300 mg of sediment using commercial extraction designed for environmental matrices rich of inhibitors (i.e., humic acids, etc.) and able to lyse microbial cells, such as DNeasy PowerSoil Pro (Qiagen), in accordance with the manufacturer's protocol. The extracted DNA shall be quantified using fluorimetric methods, such as Qubit 4 (Invitrogen), which are specific for

dsDNA and are less affected by contamination (proteic, phenol, ethanol, etc.) than absorbance-based methods. The DNA integrity shall also be evaluated using automated electrophoresis (Agilent 2100 Bioanalyser or equivalent).

The sequencing libraries shall be prepared using suitable PCR-free Sample Preparation Kits, such as Illumina TruSeq (Illumina, Inc., San Diego, CA, USA). The libraries should be quantified using automated electrophoresis and/or fluorimetric methods. Shotgun sequencing shall be performed in paired-end mode with at least 150 bp read length using next generation sequencing platforms such as Illumina NovaSeqX (Illumina, Inc., San Diego, CA, USA).

The following parameters should be recorded during the analytical procedures:

- Weight of sediment sample used for DNA extraction
- Concentration and integrity of extracted DNA
- Concentration and integrity of DNA libraries

Expression of the results

The biodiversity results shall include the number of species and taxa detected at each taxonomy level available. The results can also be elaborated through the calculation of commonly employed biodiversity indexes, both describing alpha diversity (e.g., Shannon's diversity index, Gini-Simpson diversity index) and beta diversity (e.g., Bray-Curtis distance).

Figure 5. An example of the sampling design used in the Orbetello Lagoon within the E-TRACE project for sediment collection. This design was applied at each sampling site shown in Figure 1.

6. Bioindicators for Microlitter, Contaminants, and Biomarker Analysis

6.1 Fish Bioindicators

6.1.1 Sampling Methods

For the analysis of microlitter ingestion, contaminant loads, and biomarkers responses to assess the ecotoxicological status of the lagoon by using bioindicator species, live fish shall be collected in the study area through dedicated sampling campaigns or may be obtained from local fishers active in the study area. A minimum of 15 individuals per fish species shall be sampled at each site for each sampling season selected. It may also be useful to sample individuals of the same species in an additional study area outside the selected sites, using the same methods, sampling times, and number of individuals, to serve as a control.

Once captured, animals should be kept alive until the time of sacrifice and dissection. Organisms may be dissected immediately (e.g., on board) or alternatively, they shall be kept in water with oxygenators

and transported to the laboratory for dissection. Prior to sacrifice, organisms shall be anesthetized. Immediately after sampling, each sample (whole fish or fish tissues) shall be labelled with a unique ID for each individual.

Before dissection, the following information shall be recorded for each fish sample:

- Date and time of capture
- Name of the sampling location
- Sampling method
- Latitude and longitude of each point where species are captured
- Sample size: number of individuals sampled
- Species name
- Sample ID
- Whole body weight
- Total and fork length of the fish
- Any visible deformations
- Gender (if possible)
- Maturity stage

All sampling information should be recorded on the Sampling Data Sheet (see Annex, Table A4). Below is an example of the tissues to be sampled for microlitter, contaminant, and biomarker analyses in fish, including details on preservation and storage:

- Blood samples for biomarker analysis: collect blood from the caudal vein using a disposable heparinized syringe. Use part of the blood to prepare blood smears and centrifuge an aliquot to obtain plasma samples to be preserved with antiprotease buffer at -80°C .
- Liver for biomarker analysis: weigh for somatic liver index (SLI) evaluation, take approximately 1 g or different aliquots according to the biomarker analysis to be performed, wrap in aluminium foil or put in cryovials, and immediately freeze in liquid nitrogen or on dry ice and store at -80°C .
- Muscle samples: freeze an aliquot in liquid nitrogen or on dry ice in cryovials for biomarker analysis. A separate portion for contaminant analysis can be wrapped in aluminium foil and stored at -20°C .
- Bile for biomarker analysis: collect either whole tissue or only the liquid portion using a sterile syringe. Freeze in liquid nitrogen or on dry ice in cryovials and store at -80°C .
- Kidney, gills, brain, and gonads for biomarker analysis: freeze in liquid nitrogen or on dry ice in cryovials, then store at -80°C .
- Gastrointestinal tract (GI): weigh for the fullness index (FULL). Wrap the whole GI in aluminium foil and store at -20°C for microlitter analysis.

Each tissue, stored in aluminium foil or in a cryovial/Eppendorf tube, must be labelled with a unique ID corresponding to each specimen.

6.1.2 List of materials and equipment

The materials and equipment required for fish bioindicator sampling to obtain tissues for microlitter, contaminant, and biomarker analyses are detailed below.

Materials and Equipment	Details	Purpose
Ruler or caliper	Measuring in millimeters	Measuring fish length
Balance	Precision 0.001 g	Weighing fish and tissue samples
Disposable scalpels, forceps, scissors	Fine dissection tools	Tissue dissection
Anesthetic	e.g., clove oil	Anesthetizing live animals before dissection
Aluminum foil	Contaminant-free	Wrapping tissue samples for storage
Cryoboxes and cryovials	Standard cryogenic storage containers	Storing tissue samples at low temperatures
Eppendorf tubes	1.5–2 mL tubes	Sample aliquots for biomarker analysis
Liquid nitrogen Dewar or dry ice	Cryogenic storage	Rapid freezing of tissue samples
Cooler box	Insulated storage box	Maintaining sample temperature during transport
Containers for samples	Zipped bags	Transporting and storing samples safely
Garbage bags	Standard plastic bags	Waste disposal
Gloves	Disposable, powder-free	Preventing contamination
Sampling sheets	Pre-printed field sheets	Recording sampling data
Paper towels	Laboratory paper towels	Cleaning and drying during sampling
Syringes	Including heparinized, sterile syringes	Blood and bile collection
Centrifuge	Portable centrifuge used in field sampling	Plasma extraction from blood samples

6.2 Invertebrate Bioindicators

6.2.1 Sampling Methods

Invertebrate species, such as filter-feeding organisms (e.g., mussels) and other invertebrates (e.g., crabs or polychaetes), should be collected using one of the following approaches:

- Collected directly within the study area or purchased from local fishers operating in the study area

- Collected from adjacent areas and re-located (transplanted) into the study area using cages; after an exposure period of 3–4 weeks (or longer, according to the goal of the study).

A minimum of 20 individuals per invertebrate species, for each type of analysis, shall be sampled at each site during each selected sampling season. In this case as well, it is recommended to sample additional organisms of the same species in a study area outside the selected sites, using the same methods, sampling times, and number of individuals, to serve as a control.

In the case of mussels, such as *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, a species widely used as a sentinel organism and easily transplanted into lagoon environments, different tissues and biological matrices can be sampled according to the type of analysis required. Before and during the dissection of the specimens, the following information should be recorded:

- The species name
- The total weight, shell weight, and soft tissue weight of each individual (after removing byssus filaments for mussels; measured to the fourth decimal place per individual)
- The length and width of each individual
- Any visible deformities

All sampling information should be recorded on the Sampling Data Sheet (see Annex, Table A5 and 6). To perform microlitter, contaminant, and biomarker analyses, tissues should be collected from living organisms. Alternatively, if only microlitter and contaminant analyses are planned, tissues can be dissected from specimens previously frozen at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Specimens can be analysed individually, or a pool of organisms belonging to the same size class can be created. Below are listed the tissues should be collected from invertebrate organisms (mussels) for microlitter, contaminant, and biomarker analyses, along with their respective preservation and storage procedures:

- Haemolymph for biomarker analysis: haemolymph should be withdrawn from the adductor muscle of mussels using a disposable heparinized syringe with a 23G or 18G needle. Use part of the haemolymph to obtain smears (stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).
- Hepatopancreas for biomarker or microliter analysis: the tissue should be collected and weighed on aluminium foil, placed in labelled cryogenic vials, rapidly frozen in liquid nitrogen, and stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or on dry ice. For microplastic analysis, the sample should be wrapped in aluminium foil and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.
- Gills for biomarker or microliter analysis: they should be collected, placed in labelled cryogenic vials, frozen in liquid nitrogen, and stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or dry ice. For microplastic analysis, the sample should be wrapped in aluminium foil and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.
- Mantle for contaminant analysis: the tissue should be collected, wrapped in aluminium foil, and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Each tissue, stored in aluminium foil or in a cryovial/Eppendorf tube, must be labelled with a unique ID corresponding to each specimen.

6.2.2 List of materials and equipment

The materials and equipment required for invertebrate bioindicator sampling for microlitter, contaminant, and biomarker analyses are detailed below.

Materials and Equipment	Details	Purpose
Ruler or caliper	Measuring in millimeters	Measuring fish length
Balance	Precision 0.0001 g	Weighing fish and tissue samples
Disposable scalpels, forceps, scissors	Fine dissection tools	Tissue dissection
Aluminum foil	Contaminant-free	Wrapping tissue samples for storage
Cryoboxes and cryovials	Standard cryogenic storage containers	Storing tissue samples at low temperatures
Liquid nitrogen Dewar or dry ice	Cryogenic storage	Rapid freezing of tissue samples
Cooler box	Insulated storage box	Maintaining sample temperature during transport
Containers for samples	Zipped bags	Transporting and storing samples safely
Garbage bags	Standard plastic bags	Waste disposal
Gloves	Disposable, powder-free	Preventing contamination
Sampling sheets	Pre-printed field sheets	Recording sampling data
Paper towels	Laboratory paper towels	Cleaning and drying during sampling
Syringes	Including heparinized, sterile syringes	Blood and bile collection
Smears	Microscope slides and coverslips	Preparing and storing cell or haemolymph smears for analysis

6.3 Sample Preparation and Analytical Parameters

6.3.1 Microlitter Assessment

For the analysis of microlitter in bioindicator specimens, the entire soft tissue may be analysed; alternatively, a specific tissue can be examined, such as the hepatopancreas in mussels or the gastrointestinal tract (GI) in fish. The analysed tissue, or the whole soft tissue, shall then be digested to facilitate microlitter identification, for example, using a 10% KOH solution added at a 1:5 (w:v) ratio to the tissue to be examined, and subsequently incubated at temperatures not exceeding 40 °C, as recommended by Corami et al. (2020). KOH-based digestion is typically performed for approximately 18 hours, which is the average time generally required for complete digestion of organic matter (Tsangaris et al., 2021).

The samples shall subsequently be filtered using a filtration apparatus and a vacuum pump, for example, by filtering through filters with a mesh size of 20 µm. The meshes shall then be examined under a stereomicroscope, and all particles considered potentially anthropogenic shall be isolated and characterized according to standardized methodologies, based on their shape, colour, size, and polymer type; for example, by following the Recommended Monitoring Methodologies for Microlitter described in the “Guidance on the Monitoring of Marine Litter in European Seas” developed by the European Commission, Joint Research Centre, and the MSFD Technical Group on Marine Litter (2023), or other guidelines in accordance with those applied to the other matrices considered in this study.

The parameters that should be recorded during the analysis, in order to obtain data comparable with those reported in other studies, include:

- The number of specimens analysed
- The number of specimens in which microlitter was detected
- The weight of the analysed tissues or whole organisms
- The number of isolated anthropogenic particles
- Whether naturally derived anthropogenic particles (such as cotton, rayon, or wool fibres) were considered
- The different types of particles (shape, colour, size, and polymer type) classified according to standardized methodologies
- The analytical limitations (e.g., the smallest particle isolated, the mesh size used during sample filtration, and the detection limits of the instrument employed for polymer identification)
- The percentage of the sample analysed
- The percentage of particles for which polymer identification was performed
- The use of procedural blanks

Expression of the results

Depending on the specific objectives of the study, data on the number of isolated microlitter particles can be reported in different ways. For instance, results may be expressed as the number of items per individual, calculated from the total number of particles detected and the total number of specimens analysed, or as occurrence (%), indicating the proportion of specimens in which microlitter was detected. Additionally, the percentage of the various categories of microlitter, such as shape, colour, size, and polymer type, is also typically reported.

6.3.2 Contaminant Analysis

In order to obtain a comprehensive assessment of contaminants potentially accumulating in bioindicator organisms from the investigated area, it is essential to analyse a wide range of pollutant classes associated with anthropogenic pressures. These include traditional contaminants, such as pesticides, organochlorine compounds (e.g., PCBs, HCB, and DDT), and heavy metals (Hg, Pb, Cd), as well as emerging pollutants, including perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and plastic-related compounds such as phthalate esters (PAEs) and brominated flame retardants (PBDEs).

The analysis of these contaminants in bioindicator organisms can be performed on a specific tissue aliquot, such as muscle in fish species, which also represents the edible portion and may therefore

indicate a potential route of human exposure. In the case of invertebrates, such as mussels, analyses can be conducted on the mantle or on a portion of the whole organism.

A portion of each sample should be freeze-dried and subsequently processed following the most appropriate methodology according to the contaminant class. For organochlorine compounds (OCs), the analytical procedure EPA 8081/8082, with modifications as described by Capanni et al. (2024), can be applied using capillary gas chromatography.

Phthalate esters can be extracted following the method proposed by Santini et al. (2024); the procedure involves extraction and purification steps using QuEChERS, followed by analysis through gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS).

Perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) can be analysed following established methodologies for biological matrices, such as EPA 8327. The analytical workflow involves extraction and purification using solid-phase extraction (SPE) cartridges, with final quantification performed by liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) (Rehman et al., 2023).

The determination of heavy metals, such as mercury, in biological samples can be performed following a methodology that includes a pretreatment with nitric acid and hydrogen peroxide for hot mineralization, followed by analysis using atomic absorption spectrometry with the cold vapor technique (CVAAS). Other trace metals can be quantified by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). The use of procedural blanks and certified standard reference materials (SRMs) ensures data quality and analytical accuracy.

During the analytical procedures, the following parameters should be recorded:

- The type of tissue analysed
- The lipid content of the analysed tissue
- The water content of the analysed tissue
- The amount of tissue analysed

Expression of the results

The amount of contaminants measured in sediment can be expressed in different ways depending on their abundance and on how they are commonly reported in the literature (e.g., ng/g, mg/kg). Values are typically reported on a wet weight or lipid weight basis.

6.3.3 Biomarker Analysis

To assess the ecotoxicological effects on the selected bioindicator organisms, several biological processes can be evaluated, including detoxification and biotransformation pathways, oxidative stress, neurotoxicity, and endocrine-metabolic toxicity. The various biological responses (endpoints) can be correlated with the different environmental stressors affecting the target species (Pedà et al., 2022).

In addition, gene expression analyses can be conducted using total RNA extracted from target tissues, with mRNA levels quantified through reverse transcription quantitative PCR (RT-qPCR) (Limonta et al., 2021). Molecular markers can be investigated in response to endocrine-disrupting compounds (e.g., steroid and thyroid nuclear receptors), xenobiotic-induced genes (e.g., glutathione S-transferase and cytochrome P450, CYP), oxidative stress, apoptotic, and inflammatory processes. Observed biological

responses can then be correlated with microlitter levels, as well as with both conventional and emerging contaminants measured in the same organisms and in the corresponding environmental matrices.

Analyses can be performed on different target tissues, depending on the biomarkers under investigation. Biomarkers should be selected based on the level of biological responses and in relation to the main effects associated with anthropogenic pressures and climate change impacts (e.g., exposure to conventional and emerging contaminants, microlitter, and potential alterations of environmental physicochemical conditions). The primary biomarkers that can be selected may reflect:

- Molecular-level effects (e.g., DNA damage, alterations in gene expression, changes in protein levels)
- Tissue-level effects (e.g., histological and histopathological alterations)
- Cellular-level effects (e.g., alterations of cell functions)

During the analytical procedures, the following parameters should be recorded:

- Experimental conditions (e.g., wild-caught or transplanted organisms)
- Species
- Tissue analysed
- Biomarkers assessed

Expression of the results

Depending on the biomarkers analysed, results may be expressed in different ways; generally, it is recommended to refer to how the data are reported in the literature. Depending on the objectives of the monitoring, results can also be expressed as changes relative to values measured in control organisms.

Bibliography

- Campani, T., Casini, S., Caliani, I., Pretti, C., Fossi, M.C., 2020. Ecotoxicological Investigation in Three Model Species Exposed to Elutriates of Marine Sediments Inoculated With Bioplastics. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 7, 229. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2020.00229>
- Cananzi, G., Gregori, I., Martino, F., Li, T., Boscari, E., Camatti, E., Congiu, L., Marino, I.A.M., Pansera, M., Schroeder, A., Zane, L., 2022. Environmental DNA metabarcoding reveals spatial and seasonal patterns in the fish community in the Venice Lagoon. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 9, 1009490. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.1009490>
- Capanni, F., Karamanlidis, A.A., Dendrinou, P., Zaccaroni, A., Formigaro, C., D'Agostino, A., Marsili, L., 2024. Monk seals (*Monachus monachus*) in the Mediterranean Sea: The threat of organochlorine contaminants and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. *Science of The Total Environment* 915, 169854. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.169854>
- Corami, F., Rosso, B., Roman, M., Picone, M., Gambaro, A., Barbante, C., 2020. Evidence of small microplastics (<100 μm) ingestion by Pacific oysters (*Crassostrea gigas*): A novel method of extraction, purification, and analysis using Micro-FTIR. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 160, 111606. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2020.111606>
- Di Capua, I., Piredda, R., Mazzocchi, M.G., Zingone, A., 2021. Metazoan diversity and seasonality through eDNA metabarcoding at a Mediterranean long-term ecological research site. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 78, 3303–3316. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsab059>
- Djurhuus, A., Port, J., Closek, C.J., Yamahara, K.M., Romero-Maraccini, O., Walz, K.R., Goldsmith, D.B., Michisaki, R., Breitbart, M., Boehm, A.B., Chavez, F.P., 2017. Evaluation of Filtration and DNA Extraction Methods for Environmental DNA Biodiversity Assessments across Multiple Trophic Levels. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 4, 314. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00314>
- Eichmiller, J.J., Miller, L.M., Sorensen, P.W., 2016. Optimizing techniques to capture and extract environmental DNA for detection and quantification of fish. *Molecular Ecology Resources* 16, 56–68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.12421>
- European Commission. Joint Research Centre., MSFD Technical Group on Marine Litter., 2023. Guidance on the monitoring of marine litter in European seas: an update to improve the harmonised monitoring of marine litter under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive. Publications Office, LU.
- ICRAM, 2021. Programma di monitoraggio per il controllo dell'ambiente marino-costiero (triennio 2001-2003). Metodologie analitiche di riferimento.
- Lavrador, A.S., Amaral, F.G., Moutinho, J., Vieira, P.E., Costa, F.O., Duarte, S., 2024. Comprehensive DNA metabarcoding-based detection of non-indigenous invertebrates in recreational marinas through a multi-substrate approach. *Marine Environmental Research* 200, 106660. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2024.106660>
- Leray, M., Yang, J.Y., Meyer, C.P., Mills, S.C., Agudelo, N., Ranwez, V., Boehm, J.T., Machida, R.J., 2013. A new versatile primer set targeting a short fragment of the mitochondrial COI region for

- metabarcoding metazoan diversity: application for characterizing coral reef fish gut contents. *Front Zool* 10, 34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-9994-10-34>
- Limonta, G., Mancina, A., Abelli, L., Fossi, M.C., Caliani, I., Panti, C., 2021. Effects of microplastics on head kidney gene expression and enzymatic biomarkers in adult zebrafish. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part C: Toxicology & Pharmacology* 245, 109037. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpc.2021.109037>
- Maiello, G., Bellodi, A., Cariani, A., Carpentieri, P., Carugati, L., Cicala, D., Ferrari, A., Follesa, C., Ligas, A., Sartor, P., Sbrana, A., Shum, P., Stefani, M., Talarico, L., Mariani, S., Russo, T., 2024. Fishing in the gene-pool: implementing trawl-associated eDNA metaprobe for large scale monitoring of fish assemblages. *Rev Fish Biol Fisheries* 34, 1293–1307. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11160-024-09874-y>
- Pedà, C., Romeo, T., Panti, C., Caliani, I., Casini, S., Marsili, L., Campani, T., Baini, M., Limonta, G., de Rysky, E., Caccamo, L., Perdichizzi, A., Gai, F., Maricchiolo, G., Consoli, P., Fossi, M.C., 2022. Integrated biomarker responses in European seabass *Dicentrarchus labrax* (Linnaeus, 1758) chronically exposed to PVC microplastics. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 129488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.129488>
- Rehman, A.U., Crimi, M., Andreescu, S., 2023. Current and emerging analytical techniques for the determination of PFAS in environmental samples. *Trends in Environmental Analytical Chemistry* 37, e00198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.teac.2023.e00198>
- Sanches, T.M., Schreier, A.D., 2020. Optimizing an eDNA protocol for estuarine environments: Balancing sensitivity, cost and time. *PLoS ONE* 15, e0233522. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0233522>
- Santini, S., Baini, M., Martellini, T., Bissoli, M., Galli, M., Concato, M., Fossi, M.C., Cincinelli, A., 2024. Novel ultrasound assisted extraction and d-SPE clean-up for the analysis of multiple legacy and emerging organic contaminants in edible fish. *Food Chemistry* 138582. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2024.138582>
- Shu, L., Ludwig, A., Peng, Z., 2020. Standards for Methods Utilizing Environmental DNA for Detection of Fish Species. *Genes* 11, 296. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes11030296>
- Suarez-Menendez, M., Planes, S., Garcia-Vazquez, E., Ardura, A., 2020. Early Alert of Biological Risk in a Coastal Lagoon Through eDNA Metabarcoding. *Front. Ecol. Evol.* 8, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2020.00009>
- Tsangaris, C., Panti, C., Compa, M., Pedà, C., Digka, N., Baini, M., D'Alessandro, M., Alomar, C., Patsiou, D., Giani, D., Romeo, T., Deudero, S., Fossi, M.C., 2021. Interlaboratory comparison of microplastic extraction methods from marine biota tissues: A harmonization exercise of the Plastic Busters MPAs project. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 164, 111992. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2021.111992>
- Valsecchi, E., Arcangeli, A., Lombardi, R., Boyse, E., Carr, I.M., Galli, P., Goodman, S.J., 2021. Ferries and Environmental DNA: Underway Sampling From Commercial Vessels Provides New Opportunities for Systematic Genetic Surveys of Marine Biodiversity. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 8, 704786. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.704786>

Valsecchi, E., Bylemans, J., Goodman, S.J., Lombardi, R., Carr, I., Castellano, L., Galimberti, A., Galli, P., 2020. Novel universal primers for metabarcoding environmental DNA surveys of marine mammals and other marine vertebrates. *Environmental DNA* 2, 460–476. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.72>

Table A2. Sampling Data Sheet for Surface and Water Column Samples

SAMPLE ID		
SAMPLING AREA		
SURFACE WATERS (S): Manta trawl <input type="checkbox"/> WP2 <input type="checkbox"/>	WATER COLUMN: WP2 <input type="checkbox"/> In-Situ PUMP <input type="checkbox"/>	
DATE	E-DNA: Volume of water (L)	
COORDINATES	START	END
LONGITUDE		
LATITUDE		
TIME		
VESSEL SPEED		
DURATION OF THE TRAWL		
FLOWMETER START		
FLOWMETER END		
DEPTH (m)		
WEATHER CONDITIONS	Sea:	Water Temp. (°C):
	Sky:	Wind:
BATHYMETRY		

Table A3. Sampling Data Sheet for Multiple Stressors in Sediment Samples

Sampling location	Sampling data	Note

ID sample	Latitude	Longitude	eDNA	Hg	PAEs	MPs	OCs	PFA

Table A4. Sampling Data Sheet for Multiple Stressors in Fish Bioindicators: Biomarkers Contaminants and Microlitter

Sampling location	Sampling data	Note

ID code	Sex	Tot. length (cm)	Fork length (cm)	Tot. weight (g)	GI weight (g)	Muscle aliq.					Liver weight (g)	N°. liver aliq.			Bile	Gills	Brain	Kidney		Gonad weight (g)	Blood smears	Plasma	Blood clotted	Comet	Whole blood		
						PAEs	Biom	OCs	Hg	PFA		Biom	Exp. gen	Hg				Biom	Hg								

Table A5. Sampling Data Sheet for Multiple Stressors in Invertebrate (Mussel) Bioindicators: Contaminants and Microlitter

Sampling location	Sampling data	Note

Sample ID	Tot. lenght (cm)	Total Weight (g)	Shell Weight (g)	Soft tissue Weight (g)	MPs	Harvey metal	OCs	PAEs	PFAS

